

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

 Ref. Ares(2025)3513017 - 30/04/2025

D2.3 The CO3 Framework

Dissemination Level:	PU - Public
Work Package:	WP2 Theory and CO3 model development
Document ID:	D2.3 The CO3 Framework
Delivery Date:	30 April, 2025
Type:	R – Document, report
Version:	FV1
Author(s):	Anna Björk, Maria Malho, Johannes Jauhiainen (DRI); all partners
Reviewer(s):	Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, Roman Zinigrad (AUP)

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Version history			
Version	Date	Modifications	Authors
DV1	17 April 2025		Anna Björk, Maria Malho, Johannes Jauhiainen (DRI); all partners
DV2	24 April 2025	Review	Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, Roman Zinigrad (AUP)
FV1	30 April 2025	Comments adjusted	Anna Björk, Maria Malho, Johannes Jauhiainen (DRI) Approved by Emilia Palonen (UH)

Related documents	
Other CO3 deliverables	<p>D2.1 The Social Contract: History, Theory, and Contemporary Challenges</p> <p>D2.2 Report on the Deep Roots of Social Contract</p> <p>D3.1 Report of Country Case Methodology</p> <p>D4.1 Social Media Database of EP 2024 and Ethnographic Observations</p>

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AC/DT	Anarcho-Computational Discourse-Theoretical Approach
D	Deliverable
EP2024	European Parliament elections 2024
EPP	European People's Party
EU	European Union
FEPS	Foundation for European Progressive Studies
M	Project month
NSC	New Social Contract (Dutch political party)
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
T	Task
UN	United Nations
UNRISD	United Nations Research Institute for Social Development
WP	Work Package

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction.....	4
1.1 The CO3 project: Overview.....	4
1.2 Aims of the CO3 framework.....	6
1.3 The road to framework: Preceding research and outputs.....	7
2 Social contracts as a contemporary question.....	8
2.1 Implicit and explicit manifestations of the social contract narrative.....	8
2.2 Social contracts as a European question.....	11
2.3 Summary: The contemporary relevance of the social contract narrative.....	12
3 The CO3 framework: The first version.....	13
3.1 The building blocks and definitions.....	13
3.1.1 Time scales.....	14
3.1.2 Dimensions of resilient social contract.....	15
3.1.3 Dimensions of resilience.....	16
3.2 Initial framework for assessing the continuous construction of resilient social contracts.....	17
4 Conclusion: Towards a CO3 model for resilient social contracts.....	21

1 Introduction

1.1 The CO3 project: Overview

The CO3 project focuses on researching social contracts in a time of geopolitical turmoil marked by growing political and affective polarisation, the ecological and climate crises, the rise of populism, the decay of Welfare States, intense technology politics driven by the rapid advancement of digital technologies and most recently, trade wars. Social contracts are theories and practices, and the project champions that, as such, they should be continuously constructed. While there may be single events or momentums in which we can consider the social contract being formed, a fixed, closed up contract will not survive the pressures from surrounding societal, social and political challenges and crises. If social contracts are continuously (re)constructed, they require a normative theory to assess how they should evolve. Resilience, as a capacity to evolve throughout time to resist shocks and contestation, is a valued tool for our analysis. Our use of resilience leads us to combine theoretical and empirical research alike, covering historical, sociological and political dimensions. To better understand what gives a social contract resilience, the project combines theoretical and empirical research and reaches from historical to future time.

The consortium consists of a multidisciplinary group of researchers across ten partner organisations. The project design, ways of working, and the shared ethos subscribe to the central idea of collaboration, be it our research activities or the efforts towards impact creation.

This framework is a transition point between our theoretical and historical analysis and our empirical research, sitting between phase 1 and phase 2 of the CO3 project (see figure 1). This output will be tested, contested and reflected upon over phases 2 and 3, in which the project's central arguments are being forged and developed. The framework will be revisited and reworked into its final form, the CO3 model (see sections 1.2 and 4).

The overall objective of the CO3 project is to develop and promote a more democratic, more inclusive, and more open model of social contracts, which manifests political and social resilience in the face of major societal challenges, crises and anti-democratic tendencies. In terms of specific objectives, the project will:

- Research, generate and apply theoretical and historical evidence of the continuous construction of social contracts as legacy, including their scope, limitations and key questions. This project also aims to analyse this legacy in the light of theories on European integration and development of the EU.
- Research and analyse the meaning of this legacy over time and across both EU member states and non-member states by focusing especially on long-term political, economic and social developments and challenges that generate societal frictions by contesting the scope of social contracts. Such frictions include tensions between

minorities and majorities, affective polarisation, segregation, as well as gender and diversity.

- Investigate and project the role of the EU in supporting and accommodating open and resilient social contracts by analysing empirical country cases (Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Portugal, Sweden; and Bosnia-Herzegovina, Turkey, Ukraine), EP2024 elections and policy.
- Theorise and research how crises, understood as challenges that have significant impacts on society, distinctly shape social contracts, including the emerging conceptualisation of ecosocial contracts.
- Identify safeguards in support of the resilience of democratic social contracts and develop policy responses as possible mechanisms to reinforce them by applying the theoretical and empirical findings of CO3 to a qualitative and co-creative scenario process.
- Develop an applicable Continuous Contract Construction (CO3) model of social contracts in support of inclusive ecological transformation, citizen involvement and wellbeing.
- Conduct active dissemination and stakeholder engagement to support the uptake of the CO3 model and its application to diverse political contexts.

Figure 1. Organisation and general workflow of the CO3 project.

1.2 Aims of the CO3 framework

This deliverable includes the first stage version of the CO3 *model*. The final model will show how the CO3 research results can be incorporated into an applicable framework. The end result will inform policymakers, researchers, experts and citizens alike about the key factors for ensuring and supporting the resilience of democratic social contracts. Since the final version will be based fully on the research findings, it will only be created at the end of the project (M36, January 2027). It will combine and synthesise findings from each of the temporal layers in the project from theoretical and empirical analyses, a transdisciplinary scenario process, and stakeholder interaction sessions in the Democracy Labs¹.

Rather than a finalised model, the first iteration presented below is a *framework*, timed to wrap up the project's phase 1 (see figure 1). It consists of the development of social contract theory and the event-historical deep roots of the practised social contracts across the cultural and geographical cases. Therefore, this first version of the CO3 framework is a composition of the project's findings and learnings so far, aiming to provide a reflection point for the empirical work after the country cases have been executed. It is a way to develop the consortium's theoretical and empirical analyses as a joint effort towards the final outputs of the project.

The framework is also a step forward in considering and evaluating the implementation of the research plan from a methodological point of view. The ten country cases, which will be conducted in phase 2, are based on a mixed methodology as each country case will have a different design. As the project does not conduct a systematic comparative analysis, syntheses need to be generated through other means. For example, at the end of D2.2, the final section provides a cross-fertilising analysis of the deep roots of the country cases' social contracts, which allows for the identification of points of conjuncture and difference between country cases. Overall, the research plan includes tasks that are especially designed to support this: T2.5, resulting in D2.3 (this framework); T5.1 and T5.2, resulting in D5.2 (report on crises); T6.1 and T6.2, resulting in D6.1 (drivers and scenarios); and the final mode of this output (CO3 model).

These mechanisms aim not only to ensure the mitigation of the potential risks of methodological pluralism (for an elaboration, see D3.1) but also to alleviate the implications of methodological nationalism. The latter refers to how we are currently building up our empirical research through national country cases. Contrary to the traditional understanding of social contracts, we develop an understanding of social contracts that does not subscribe to methodological nationalism, but reaches beyond that. We will reflect on the role and effects of our methodological choices continuously and assess our findings from this perspective. In practice, this happens through collaborative workshops, joint writing

¹ Using the world café methodology, they engage lay citizens in discussing the potential new social contracts, thereby informing the CO3 consortium about the reception of the project's perspectives and findings, and creating impact through open discussion with citizens.

processes and scientific panels in conferences. Most importantly, the CO3 project design has been planned to include collaborative analytical work across the project's timeline, enabling us to develop our work towards our theoretical, empirical and methodological aims as a collective.

1.3 The road to framework: Preceding research and outputs

As noted, the framework sits at the intersection of three work packages:

- WP2 – Theory and CO3 model development
- WP3 – Constructions and frictions of social contracts
- WP4 – Contemporary debates, bases and challenges of the social contract

As part of these WPs, the following deliverables have already been finalised:

- D2.1 The Social Contract: History, Theory, and Contemporary Challenges
- D2.2 Report on the Deep Roots of Social Contract
- D3.1 Report of Country Case Methodology
- D4.1 Social Media Database of EP 2024 and Ethnographic Observations

Furthermore, the work towards the D4.3 Multi-method framework for the analysis of contemporary visions of social contract has proceeded to a phase where the outline of the country reports and philosophy behind the EP2024 study has been written out (AC/DT approach) and combined with the indicators for the secondary survey data analysis. Also, the D4.2 Country reports (of eight EU member states) have been advanced for submission as part of the first project review (M17, June 2025).

In practice, the work for D2.1 and D2.2 (the theoretical and historical perspectives to social contracts) have had the most explicit influence on this framework. In section 3, we summarise some of the key elements from these deliverables and translate them into questions to be asked in the next phases of the project. The work done for the D4.1 in WP4, focusing on the EP2024 elections and social media data, has increased our understanding of the possibilities of analysing contemporary social contracts through utterances, discourses, and particular concepts and themes. These learnings have also contributed to the list of questions below. As part of the work, we have also organised a workshop with the consortium on the aims and possibilities of the framework and requested additional comments for the first drafts. Over the first year, the consortium members have also taken part in conferences and joint working sessions regarding the project's main themes in, for example, Dublin, Paris and online. Despite the preparatory work and iterative process, however, the full potential and possible pitfalls of the framework can only be properly assessed as the empirical work progresses.

2 Social contracts as a contemporary question

2.1 Implicit and explicit manifestations of the social contract narrative

As the CO3 project research progresses, it also moves from historical social contracts (both in theory and practice) towards its contemporary, and future applications. As the first step towards bringing together the different temporal layers of the research, we showcase some of the recent examples of how social contracts have been used and manifested in public discourses. This ultimately has some practical implications for the final version of the CO3 model: to address ongoing political and societal undercurrents and developments and to gain any ground as an applicable tool, it needs to resonate with discourses, uses and scopes of the social contract in its contemporary forms. While what we have listed below constitutes only a brief glance, the examples still point at a promising horizon for our work, both in terms of bringing together the theoretical, conceptual and practical dimensions of social contracts and in terms of deepening the analysis of its current relevance and potential.

Recently, references to and reflections on the social contract have been actively brought up by European parties, EU institutions, and national decision-makers. The concept of social contracts has also appeared in reports and policy papers by UN organisations and international organisations such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). In these contexts, the reference points for the concept of the social contract vary. The ambiguity of use opens up a variety of interpretations of its meaning in various, context-bound ways, and marks the social contract as an essentially contested concept² that, at times, even shows up as an empty signifier.³ As part of the next phases of our research in years two and three of the project, we will take the opportunity to analyse some of the current uses of the social contract through a systematic approach, drawing on both our theoretical and empirical research.

In the examples below, we can identify some recurring uses of the social contract in public discussion. These include competitiveness, intergenerational fairness, care, social cohesion, national identity, integration of immigrants, and green transitions. Often, but not always, the context in which stakeholders identify a need to reflect or build upon social contracts is linked to societal transitions and transformations such as green transitions or labour market

² Gallie, W. B.. "Essentially Contested Concepts". *The Importance of Language*, edited by Max Black, Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1969, pp. 121-146. <https://doi.org/10.7591/9781501741319-010>.
Collier, D., Daniel Hidalgo, F., & Olivia Maciuceanu, A. (2006). Essentially contested concepts: Debates and applications. *Journal of Political Ideologies*, 11(3), 211–246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13569310600923782>;

³ Laclau, Ernesto. "8.5 'Why do empty signifiers matter in politics?'". *Deconstruction: A Reader*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2001, pp. 405-413. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781474470919-047>

transitions. It is important to note that the examples listed here are limited and not based on a systematic review, so it is possible that the list is not exhaustive. It includes both examples where 1) the social contract has a relatively clear reference point (e.g. the labour market, intergenerational justice, national security), and 2) the social contract as an umbrella term is referencing several topics and issues (the characteristics of a future ideal society; including informal labour markets and culture).

Examples: National level references to the social contract in recent cases

- In France, President Emmanuel Macron organised a roundtable discussion in 2018 for union leaders to discuss the basis of a new social contract.⁴ Similarly in Finland, Prime Minister Juha Sipilä led a process in 2014–2015 on forming a new social contract through talks among labour unions and industry leaders in order to enhance competitiveness.⁵ Both examples reference the social contract as an economic social contract through labour market and union politics, and as part of the steering and implementation of economic policy at the national level.
- Concerning using the social contract in connection with intergenerational fairness, Keir Starmer, Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, wrote an op-ed published in the Sunday Times in 2025 in which he underlined the need for political change to rebuild the country's social contract. In the op-ed, Starmer focused particularly on the disillusionment of young people and framed the social contract through a lens of intergenerational justice.⁶
- The social contract has also been used in reference to national identity and immigration. One example of such a concept was developed by the German sociologist Bassam Tibi in 1998, called *Leitkultur*. It intertwines national identity and the social contract with a framework of core cultural values that immigrants are expected to adopt to integrate successfully into German society and become part of the prevailing social contract.⁷ Another example can be found in France, where the notions of *République* and secularism or *laïcité* are often linked to the social contract and national identity of the country.⁸
- In the Netherlands, Pieter Omtzigt, a seasoned Dutch politician, has used the social contract as a broader term to describe an ideal society. In 2021, Omtzigt authored a manifesto called *Een nieuw sociaal contract* (A New Social Contract). The manifesto outlines his vision for political reform in the Netherlands, highlighting the need for a new social security system, amongst others. After leaving his former party, Omtzigt founded the New Social Contract (NSC) party in August 2023. Under his leadership, the NSC secured 20 out of 150 seats in the Dutch House of Representatives in the 2023 elections.

⁴ France Inter. (2023, September 15). *Le contrat social, version Macron* [Radio broadcast]. Radio France.

⁵ Finnish Government. (2015, August 20). *Negotiations on social contract terminated*.

⁶ Starmer, K. (2025, February 14). *Keir Starmer: I have sympathy for Gen Z, but they can't just opt out*. *The Times*

⁷ Tibi, B. (2000). *Europa ohne Identität? Die Krise der multikulturellen Gesellschaft*. Siedler Verlag.

⁸ Barras, A. (2010). Contemporary *Laïcité*: Setting the Terms of a New Social Contract? The Slow Exclusion of Women Wearing Headscarves. *Totalitarian Movements and Political Religions*, 11(2), 229–248.

Beyond the national contexts, examples from international organisations such as the OECD and the United Nations Research Institute for Social Development (UNRISD) show that social contracts can be linked with globally driven initiatives. In 2022, the OECD issued a report that examines how informal employment affects the feeling of attachment of individuals to the society's prevailing social contract and how, by extension, the social contract may suffer if the informal employment sector grows.⁹ In the same year, the UNRISD published a report in 2022 focusing on the growth of inequality globally while also calling for a new eco-social contract. More specifically, the report by UNRISD notes that 'real-world social contracts tend to be far removed from a notion of free and equal persons creating a society based upon rules to which all agree', and that they rather 'reflect existing power structures and inequalities at multiple levels and in varied forms, often creating de facto contracts of domination'. To mitigate this domination tendency, the UNRISD report promotes a new ecosocial contract, which would be sustainable if there was a broad consensus regarding the questions of what the common public goods are. These include, according to UNRISD, keeping global warming under 1.5°C, providing decent work for all, and maintaining global peace and security in line with the UN Charter.¹⁰

The claim that the scope of the social contract should have an ecosocial reach has gained ground especially since 2020. There has been a growing number of interventions that link the social contract with green transitions by deploying this term.¹¹ In these contexts, stakeholders often shed light on the ongoing climate crisis and call for a new social contract that would take into consideration the planetary boundaries. One example of such an intervention includes the declaration *Just Transition: A New Social Contract for the Wellbeing of People and the Planet*, issued by the Foundation for European Progressive Studies (FEPS), civil society network SOLIDAR, and a broad coalition of civil society organisations, trade unions, social economy enterprises, and think tanks: it calls upon European Ministers for Environment and Energy, as well as EU and national decision-makers, to integrate environmental and climate policies with social policies.¹²

In terms of the forthcoming work in the CO3 project, the articulations above exemplify the issue of the extension of social contract theories regarding their scope and content (see D2.1, Contribution 8). In the next phases of research, we will strengthen the link between political and social challenges, their problematisations and narratives, and social contract theories to investigate how they could and should evolve.

⁹ OECD. (2024). *Informality and globalisation: In search of a new social contract*. OECD Publishing.

¹⁰ United Nations Research Institute for Social Development. (2022). *Crises of inequality: Shifting power for a new eco-social contract*. UNRISD.

¹¹ United Nations Research Institute for Social Development. (2022). *Crises of inequality: Shifting power for a new eco-social contract*. UNRISD.

¹² Foundation for European Progressive Studies (FEPS), & SOLIDAR. (2023, July 11). *Just Transition: A New Social Contract for the Wellbeing of People and the Planet – A Call to Action by European stakeholders*.

2.2 Social contracts as a European question

The term "social contract" has circulated across various EU contexts – from party manifestos and statements by EU leaders to reports by EU institutions. The term remains broad and loosely defined within EU discourse, although it often emerges in the context of societal or policy transitions. D2.1 set the theoretical context for how to understand the role of the EU from the perspective of the social contract, and the normative idea of the European social contract. In addition to the theoretical contributions, phase 1 of our research also conducted a study of the themes that were discussed in the European Parliamentary elections of 2024. Although the analysis is still ongoing, it aims to address how the social contract can be thought of in terms of these themes, and what the social contract would mean to different political actors and the voters. We aim to shed light on the question of whether there can be a Social Contract in Europe without Social Europe. As a complementary analysis, phase 1 also includes an analysis of extensive, existing European level survey data and its organisation into a set of social contract indicators. This ongoing work will, in the next phases, inform our analysis over the European social contract or the EU social contract.

Examples: References to the Social Contract in EU level discourse

- In a statement delivered by the EU to the UN Commission for Social Development in February 2025, the social contract was presented as a framework through which one could develop a human-centred approach to human rights, social cohesion, solidarity, and decent work, through which the UN's Sustainable Development Goals could be achieved.¹³ The social cohesion framework to social contracts has also been applied in other EU contexts. For example, in a final report published in 2023 by a group of high-level specialists on the future of Cohesion Policy set up by the Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, the authors argued that the social contract is based on solidarity among different groups.
- A similarly broad framework to the social contract has circulated in manifestos of European political parties. For example, in the 2019 party manifesto of the European Socialists, titled 'A New European Social Contract', the issues associated with a "new social contract" included inequality, tax justice, climate change, harnessing Europe's digital revolution, agricultural transformation, migration, and security.¹⁴ Five years later the European Socialists think tank again called for a new European social contract, this time focusing on just and green transitions.¹⁵
- The European People's Party (EPP) has mentioned both social contracts and societal contracts in manifestos, press releases, and public declarations. For example, in a paper published in 2022, the EPP called for a new post-COVID social contract with regards to

¹³ European Union. (2025, February 5). *EU Statement – UN Commission for Social Development – General Discussion*. European External Action Service.

¹⁴ Party of European Socialists. (2019). *A new social contract for Europe*.

¹⁵ Foundation for European Progressive Studies. (2024). *Just Transition: A New Social Contract for the Wellbeing of People and the Planet – A Call to Action by European stakeholders*.

decarbonisation.¹⁶ A few years before that, the EPP welcomed the EU's first strategy on care, calling it a hallmark of our societal contract, through generations.¹⁷

2.3 Summary: The contemporary relevance of the social contract narrative

In contrast with the theoretical work in D2.1, where we saw that social contract theories are theories reflecting their historical contexts, the examples above demonstrate the existing desire to reshape and reconstruct a social contract at the EU level. However, for the time being, there is a lack of a unified theory for a social contract that would work at this level. To address this gap, we continue to combine the theoretical and empirical legacy of the social contract with its contemporary theoretical and practical developments. In the following phases of the project, we will strengthen our mapping and analysis of the contemporary use of the social contract as a concept in the debate, both as an explicit term and as constructed through key challenge points. Importantly, we will continue to explore its applicability and varied meaning across contexts in policy and other public forums. Eventually, our theoretical and empirical research will be used as an analytical background for assessing the scope and meaning of the concept of the social contract, not only as it is being used in examples, but also discussing its explanatory and normative potential. This will culminate at the end of the project, with the publication of the final CO3 model, policy recommendations and a policy brief.

As indicated in the deliverable D2.1, the backdrop for understanding which ways social contracts are being challenged is especially visible in the light of three developments. First, the rise of the non-national institutions, such as the EU, fundamentally challenges the focus on the nation state as a pre-commitment of social contract theories. In CO3 research, we critically reflect on the implications of methodological nationalism and aim to develop analytical ways forward from this perspective. Transcending this premise is by design – by already adopting the perspective of the EU in our theoretical and historical research – providing us with a recurrent reflection point on the challenges of methodological nationalism. However, this choice alone will most likely not solve the issue, which is why we will assess it at different points of research, e.g., in the context of crises and scenario work (to be organised in WP5).

Second, the rise of polarisation, in particular affective polarisation, challenges the possibility of individuals to reach a consensus over shared rules. Considering that polarisation now cuts across divides based on gender, geography, socioeconomic background, and national borders, this political, social, and historical trend requires us to rethink the possibility that the social contract as an agreement can be achieved in the first place. Increasing the

¹⁶ European People's Party. (2020, October 14). *EPP position paper: Decarbonising Europe's economy with ambition*.

¹⁷ European People's Party Group. (2022, September 7). *Care is hallmark of societal contract which must be empowered*.

capabilities for assessing and understanding where, through which means, and between whom social contracts are being forged and reconstructed becomes a crucial element for conducting politics and reinforcing democratic governance.

Third and finally, the increasing importance of climate concerns emphasises the need to broaden the scope of traditional social contract theories to consider the form, scope and limits of the ecosocial contract (see D2.1, D2.2). Beyond agency, the environmental and climate crises require the consideration of near term and long term effects, synchronous and asynchronous tipping points, ultimately challenging the temporality of social contracts. Therefore, the intersection of analysing the impact of the polycrisis alongside the environmental dimension of social contracts is one of the key challenges for contemporary debates.

Some of the examples in sections 2.1 and 2.2 reflect these key challenges. In our future work, we aim at also understanding more deeply the differences between the challenges in a qualitative sense: since they are not just distinct challenges in a thematic sense, but also in the way they put pressure on social contracts. For example, the extension of the "borders" of social contract theory (its scope) challenges a core theoretical commitment regarding the extension. However, polarisation challenges the contract by focusing on the feasibility of the agreement. Developing the nuances should also support the development of our analyses and tools.

The work in D2.2 indicates that the current social contract has to reach both towards the future and the past. On one hand, it needs to extend beyond borders and towards new generations, yet on the other hand, there are inherited conflicts and past discriminations which continue to influence current social contracts. In the course of our work, the analysis of the interlinkages between the challenges identified in our research and the examples in the contemporary discourse on the social contract will be developed.

3 The CO3 framework: The first version

3.1 The building blocks and definitions

As explained above, the CO3 project ultimately aims at strengthening the political and social resilience of European societies by providing a means for understanding and building a more democratic, inclusive and open model of social contracts. This type of social contract will, apart from supporting democracy and resilience, also take into account citizen involvement and wellbeing and the perspective of an inclusive ecological transformation.

To meet this aim, the CO3 project has a twofold ambition. Theoretically, it studies how the contemporary theories of social contracts contribute to our understanding of the social contracts in the current crisis-driven European political environment. Empirically, it investigates the contradictions and tensions between practices, narratives, and lived

experiences in social contracts across European countries through 10 concrete country cases.

The conceptual work, as well as the data collection and analysis in the CO3 project, has an embedded temporal structure as its backbone. Understanding social contract construction through different time scales sheds light on the temporalities and historical layers in socio-political concepts, and enables the creation of a knowledge base of resilient social contracts over time in different local, national, regional, or transnational contexts. This approach aims at providing tools for promoting the continuous construction of resilient social contracts through public governance and long-term policymaking.

To support and frame the next phases of the project, we are drawing on the extensive theoretical and historical work that has been conducted in phase 1. We have already referred to the work done in our preceding deliverables in sections 1 and 2 of this deliverable. Below, we are building on this work by bringing together the elements of

- the temporal layers (long-term, medium-term, short-term);
- the dimensions of resilient social contract; and
- the dimensions of resilience.

Considering that the project's key aim is to understand, and to provide a model for supporting, resilient social contracts, we here introduce a way to organise the temporal layers around a set of questions (see table 1). The questions are embedding learnings from the previously finalised deliverables (listed above), and seek to allow room for the empirical cases to develop also independently. By applying these questions, we will then arrive at, first, to a point where we will consider the collected data against the resilient social contract dimensions, and finally the more fine-tuned analysis of the dimensions of resilience. By doing so, we aim to arrive at a point where we begin to understand how the different dimensions of resilience play out in context, and what we could and should do to support them.

As a part of the process for building up the framework, we have had workshops and conversations among the consortium, which have added to the selection of perspectives to deal with when it comes to understanding the pressure points to social contracts. Therefore, we have also included a top frame in table 1, which includes the general tensions, trends and undercurrents affecting social contracts across the empirical cases. Their implications vary according to contextual factors, which is why their consequences to resilient social contract dimensions and the dimensions of resilience are not necessarily commonly shared, although they can be.

3.1.1 Time scales

The three time scales of the CO3 project (see figure 1) corresponding to the dimensions of continuous contract construction are briefly described below. The work for implementing them into our theoretical and empirical research design started already in D2.2. We wish to

note that the terminology of *originary*, *open* and *resilient* has been the original wording at the beginning of our work, and continues to be evaluated as the research advances.

- 1) **Long-term, originary social contract:** Social contract theories have traditionally assumed a social contract to be founded on a one-time hypothetical event between sovereign individuals. In the CO3 project, we apply this idea to examine the foundations of the originary social contract, with historical, constitutional, cultural, and other long-term perspectives on the roots of the social contract. The actualisation of the originary social contract happens through analysis, debates, and social, cultural, and political development over time, but the deep roots of the long-term dimension always remain present and form part of the top-down dimension (such as a constitution) of the social contract construction.
- 2) **Medium-term, open social contract:** As social contracts must be continuously renewed to correspond to the developing membership or the *demos*, it is essential to look at the construction of the medium-term, open social contract. To maintain itself, the social contract has to be flexible and openly integrate new populations, groups, organisations, or identities over the medium term.
- 3) **Short-term, resilient social contract:** Over the short term, it is essential to understand how crises and momentary challenges contest existing social contracts and, more importantly, how they can be overcome to help build stronger and more resilient social contracts. The short-term perspective on social contracts brings into focus the resilience of the social contracts to overcome crises and challenges, and ultimately build stronger and more resilient societies.

3.1.2 Dimensions of resilient social contract

To be able to study and build a model of resilient social contracts in the CO3 project, we created a theory-based suggestion of normative dimensions constituting resilient social contracts. As explained in detail in D2.1 (see Contribution 8, p. 97–98), the three dimensions are democratic, inclusive, and continuous. The democratic dimension refers to a society's openness to internal contestations and its ability to address diverse interests through institutions, as well as phenomena such as voting, political competition, political contestation, and public deliberation. The inclusive dimension refers to the 'systematic expansion of participation in decision-making processes to previously excluded individuals, groups, or entities' (D2.1, p. 97). The continuous dimension refers to a social contract's ability to remain 'open to renegotiation based on the recognition of overlooked interests and new challenges' (D2.1, p. 98). Based on this theoretical analysis, Contribution 2 to D2.1 argued that the level of democratic participation and inclusiveness are correlated with the continuity of the social contract. This is an important theoretical hypothesis to be tested in CO3 empirical country cases and forms an essential normative background (see figure 2 below) for connecting the theory and the practices as part of the CO3 framework and beyond the immediate project context.

Figure 2. Normative dimensions of resilient social contracts.

3.1.3 Dimensions of resilience

To build and test a framework for the continuous construction of resilient social contracts, the concept of resilience needs to be defined. As argued at length in D2.1 (Contribution 8, p. 99–103), we overcome the theoretical challenge of the stability of social contracts through a dynamic understanding of stability as *resilience*. This invites us to build an empirically informed approach for resilient social contracts and their continuous construction without altogether losing the elements relating to the stability of social contracts.

The theoretically informed definition of resilience has five separate dimensions that we understand as follows (adapted from D2.1, p. 101–102; see also figure 3 below):

1. *Robustness over equilibrium*. The primary distinction between equilibrium-based and resilience-based approaches to social contracts is the emphasis on robustness rather than sameness. The resilience-based approach acknowledges that the social contract must be continuously recalibrated to remain responsive to shifting conditions and internal contestations. Core principles such as fairness, inclusiveness, and democratic participation must be upheld, yet their practical implementation must remain flexible and adaptive.
2. *Adaptive institutions*. Under a resilient social contract, institutions must be structurally flexible to respond effectively to emerging challenges without descending into disorder. Political and legal systems should enable incremental, iterative reform, allowing for policy adjustments that account for evolving circumstances rather than

presuming the permanence of a particular institutional arrangement. Resilience is thus distinct from mere institutional durability; rather than preserving an existing order at all costs, it seeks to guide institutional change in ways that maintain core normative commitments.

3. *Pluralism*. A crucial aspect of resilient systems is that they are fueled by diversity. Much like in ecological systems, where biodiversity enhances an ecosystem’s ability to withstand shocks, institutional pluralism fosters resilience by enabling governance systems to absorb and adapt to disruptions.
4. *Disequilibrium*. A resilience-based approach embraces disequilibrium as an intrinsic aspect of societal progress. Rigid adherence to rules can suppress legitimate contestation and emergent concerns. In contrast, resilience-oriented justice systems recognise that uncertainty and disruption can serve as catalysts for transformation.
5. *Feedback loops and learning mechanisms*. A resilient social contract should integrate continuous feedback mechanisms to assess its effectiveness and make necessary adjustments. Democracy in its many forms and mechanisms (elections, public deliberation, association, contestations) allows for such feedback mechanisms to operate.

Figure 3. Definition of resilience as dynamic understanding of stability with five dimensions.

3.2 Initial framework for assessing the continuous construction of resilient social contracts

Based on these building blocks and definitions set by our robust research on the theory and history of social contracts, we have created an initial framework for assessing the continuous construction of resilient social contracts. This framework is the starting point for the work in phases 2 and 3 of the CO3 project, and will be tested and refined through the empirical research on the 11 CO3 country cases of Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Portugal, Sweden, Türkiye, and Ukraine. At this stage of the work, whether we speak of adaptive institutions, pluralism, or feedback, these concepts need to be more precisely contextualised to be fully operationalised. We assume that this will require some additional theories to enable linking the theory with the empirics. The final evaluation will be conducted at the end of the project.

Currently, we have a theoretically informed normative framework to guide the empirical research for CO3 project: we will use it to analyse and assess the state of social contracts in the 11 European countries and the European Union, as well as to provide recommendations and suggest actions for strengthening the resilience of the social contracts against societal challenges, crises and anti-democratic tendencies. Ultimately, the CO3 framework aims to become a theoretically and empirically informed, reliable framework for the European Union, researchers, NGOs, international organisations, and other actors interested in strengthening democracy in the face of societal challenges.

The framework (see table 1) built around the three temporal dimensions of the CO3 project is complemented with key questions raised by our comprehensive theoretical research. The goal is to create a tool for assessing the possibilities for continuous construction and resilience of social contracts in the long, medium and short term. In practice, the CO3 researchers will build their cases through empirical research while the framework will serve as a point of reflection throughout the analysis and evidence accumulation process. An important point to note here is that the questions presented below do not represent the exact research topics or research questions chosen by the researchers themselves. In particular, the questions included in the framework are a way to combine and display the findings of the project's theoretical work and, therefore, to generate a joint basis for reflection and analysis throughout phase 2 of the project. To adjust the empirical research, the framework needs to remain flexible at this stage to adapt to the feedback from this work.

The framework will be the final contribution of the project. A final suggestion for a CO3 model will include the refined version of the questions and the model based on the theoretical findings, and the learnings of its use during the empirical work.

General tensions, trends and undercurrents affecting social contracts		
Urbanisation Migration Technological development Polycrises Religion EU Green transition National /supranational sovereignty Reconfiguration of personal, collective and national identities EU expansion Gender issues Welfare state (Growing) socioeconomic inequalities Social exclusions (racism, xenophobia, ableism, ageism, heteropatriarchy, gender) (Inter-)generational dimension Colonialism/neocolonialism		
1. KEY ASPECTS FOR ASSESSING THE LONG-TERM, ORIGINARY SOCIAL CONTRACT	2. KEY ASPECTS FOR ASSESSING THE MEDIUM-TERM, OPEN SOCIAL CONTRACT	3. KEY ASPECTS FOR ASSESSING THE SHORT-TERM, RESILIENT SOCIAL CONTRACT
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What kind of theory of justice or justice principles are embedded in the social contract? 2. How does the social contract relate to the concepts of general will, common good, and solidarity? 3. What are the sources of legitimacy of the social contract? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How does the social contract relate to the concepts of equality and equity? 2. How does the social contract relate to the concept of inclusion? 3. How does the social contract address the questions of welfare? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do crises affect the social contract? 2. What key issues are politicised related to the social contract during a crisis? 3. How is the relationship between supranational governance, such as

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. What is the role of consent and the 'social' in the social contract? 5. How is the democratic process organised as a <i>mixed social constitution</i>? 6. How have the legacies of imperialism, colonialism, and forms of external domination affected the social contract? 7. How has authoritarianism affected the social contract? 8. How have major political, economic, and social shifts affected the social contract? 9. How has the interplay of nationalism and transnational dynamics affected the social contract? 10. How are the top-down, bottom-up and horizontal dimensions of the social contract constructed? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. How does the social contract address the formation of the <i>demos</i> and the national/European identifications of its members? 5. Does the social contract allow hegemonic shifts and how? 6. How do social, political, and affective polarisation impact the social contract? 7. How does the social contract deal with the dynamics of conflict and consensus in society? 8. What are the cultural, social, and political points of reproduction and renewal of the social contract (the performative aspect of the social contract)? 9. Does the social contract allow for adaptations of the current social system to meet new demands and how? 10. How are the top-down, bottom-up, and 	<p>the EU, and national governance during a crisis?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. What are the elements building the resilience of the social contract, and how are they manifested? 5. What kinds of leadership does the social contract entail during a crisis? 6. What is the role of visions and the future in the social contract? 7. How are the top-down, bottom-up, and horizontal dimensions of the social contract constructed?
--	---	---

Table 1. The first version of the CO3 framework with key questions to be addressed and refined through 11 empirical country cases.

4 Conclusion: Towards a CO3 model for resilient social contracts

At this point of the work (M15 of the project), we are still in the process of transitioning from the theoretical and historical angles to the empirical work. The analytical richness of the phase 1 in the project makes the task of drafting a framework a demanding one. Furthermore, as the work has progressed, we have also gotten caught up with the back-and-forth of the conceptual work: while we are critically assessing some of our original choices and replacing them with more suitable alternatives, we are also in the process of still identifying, which conceptual and theoretical choices are the most appropriate ones to our upcoming work. This also applies to the first version of the CO3 framework, and the subsequent CO3 model in its final form: ensuring a balance between conceptual framing and choosing, while encouraging context-sensitivity and expertise, will most likely to have an end result where some viable options for key concepts, visualisations and directions are only realised afterwards.

In the next stages, we will be continuing our empirical research, and making the first joint reflections on the usefulness of this deliverable for that work. This will include, for example, talking points such as:

- How to deal with methodological nationalism?
- How to include non-traditional subjects (e.g. non-citizens, future generations) in political decision-making and social contracts and what does that mean for our theoretical work?
- How to find a balance between the different levels of governance, and the interaction between the national and EU social contracts?
- Which concepts and theoretical standpoints are commonly shared and applicable across disciplines, and which are the most contested ones?
- How should we introduce and assess the question of the rule of law, which remains an important, yet unfocused thematic for future social contracts?

Our joint work continues over the shared analyses of the role of crises in WP5, followed by the scenario work in WP6 and the preceding process for building up the drivers for the scenarios. By that time, we will also develop our learnings further in the context of a Delphi survey, where we are reaching towards long-term political development processes in support of resilient and democratic social contracts. In M36 of the project, we will have our finalised CO3 model as a public deliverable.

